

Synthesis and mass spectral studies of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} with 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and β -diketones, hydroxyaryl aldehydes or ketones

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Abstract : A series of mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) having the general formula $[\text{CoLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (where HL = 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, HL' = salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 2-hydroxybenzophenone, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione and 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione) have been synthesized and characterized. The complexes have distorted octahedral structures. The characterization of the complexes has been made on the basis of elemental analyses, conductances, TLC, magnetic moments and IR, electronic and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, cobalt(II), IR, electronic spectra, magnetic moments, FAB mass spectra.

Introduction

Cobalt complexes of the type CoL_2 with aryl aldehydes and ketones have been widely studied. Graddon and Mockler¹ have synthesized CoL_2 and CoL_2B_2 complexes (where HL = salicylaldehyde, 4-chlorosalicylaldehyde, B = H_2O , pyridine) and have studied their magnetic and spectroscopic properties. Few mixed ligand complexes of cobalt have also been reported. Salicylaldehyde and substituted salicylaldehyde complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{sal})_2\text{acphen}]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{Brsal})_2\text{acphen}]$ {where Brsal = 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, acphen = bis(acetophenone)ethylenediamine} have been synthesized by Patel *et al.*². Roy and Raman³ have prepared several complexes of the type $\text{CoL}_2\text{L}'_2$ (where HL = dibenzoylmethane, HL' = pyridine and its derivatives or quinoline and its derivatives). Thermal and spectral studies on $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})(\text{cyclam})]\text{ClO}_4$ (where cyclam = 1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane) have been carried out by Sovilj and Minic⁴. Mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{hfac})_2(\text{pyz})]$ ⁵, $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})_2(\text{im})]$ ⁶, $[\text{Co}(\text{bzac})_2(\text{im})_2]$ ⁷, $[\text{Co}(\text{hap})_2(\text{qn})_2]$ ⁸ and $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})_2(\text{cy})_2]$ ⁹ (where pyz = pyrazine, im = imidazole, qn = quinoline, cy = cyclohexamine) have also been reported. Saar¹⁰ has synthesized mixed ligand octahedral cobalt(III) complexes of the type CoLL'_2 and $\text{CoL}_2\text{L}'$ (where HL and HL' are acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane). Earlier, mixed ligand complexes of the type MLL' (where M = Cu, Zn) and $\text{MLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ (where M = Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} , Ni^{II}) have been reported from our laboratories¹¹⁻¹⁴ and in the present paper mixed ligand

complexes of the type $[\text{CoLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ {where HL = 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, HL' = salicylaldehyde (salH), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hapH), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (hppH), 2-hydroxybenzophenone (hbpH), 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (hnpH), pentane-2,4-dione (acetylacetone, acacH), 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (benzoylacetone, bzacH) and 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (dibenzoylmethane, dbzmH)} are described.

Results and discussion

The reaction of cobalt(II) nitrate with 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde and salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone or 2-hydroxybenzophenone in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Similarly the other mixed ligand complexes (Figs. 2 and 3) were synthesized. The resulting Co^{II} complexes are yellow solids. They do not melt on heating but decompose at high temperature. They are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, nitrobenzene and methanol but soluble in DMF. The properties and analyses of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The molar conductances in DMF lie in the range $2\text{--}6 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ showing the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes¹⁵.

Fig. 2

Thin layer chromatography :

The TLC of the mixed ligand complexes exhibit single spots with R_f values being intermediate of the two corresponding symmetrical bis-complexes indicating that these are mixed ligand complexes rather than a mixture of the two corresponding bis-complexes.

Infrared spectra :

The mixed ligand complexes exhibit strong absorption bands in the region $1625\text{--}1658 \text{cm}^{-1}$, which may be assigned to the coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$, whereas in free 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyace-

R^1	R^2
CH_3	CH_3
CH_3	C_6H_5
C_6H_5	C_6H_5

Fig. 3

tophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, acetylaceton and benzoylacetone bands at $1680, 1660, 1650, 1640, 1724$ and 1724cm^{-1} respectively have been reported due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$. Thus the shifting of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ to lower wave number side in the mixed ligand complexes supports the chelation of these ligands to the metal atom. Patel *et al.*² have reported similar bands due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ at $\sim 1600 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in $[\text{Co}(\text{acphen})(\text{sal})_2]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{acphen})(5\text{-Brsal})_2]$. Bands in the region $1517\text{--}1546 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the mixed ligand complexes may be due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$. In the spectra of the mixed ligand complexes, weak to medium intensity absorption bands in the region $400\text{--}440 \text{cm}^{-1}$ which are not present in the free ligands, may be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibrations. Similar bands in this region have been assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ vibrations in case of metal β -diketonates

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}

Complex	Decomp. temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Found (Calcd.) % :			μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
			C	H	Co		
$[\text{Co}(5\text{-Clisal})(\text{sal})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	280	66	44.99 (45.24)	3.39 (3.52)	15.64 (15.85)	4.28	4
$[\text{Co}(5\text{-Clisal})(\text{hap})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	270	34	46.48 (46.72)	3.68 (3.92)	15.01 (15.28)	4.26	6
$[\text{Co}(5\text{-Clisal})(\text{hpp})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	218	35	47.88 (48.08)	4.01 (4.28)	14.84 (14.74)	4.00	5
$[\text{Co}(5\text{-Clisal})(\text{hbp})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	260	42	53.45 (53.65)	3.74 (3.82)	12.97 (13.16)	4.63	2
$[\text{Co}(5\text{-Clisal})(\text{hnp})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	282	66	51.10 (51.26)	3.34 (3.58)	13.76 (13.97)	4.46	2
$[\text{Co}(5\text{-Clisal})(\text{acac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	208	45	41.08 (41.22)	4.12 (4.32)	16.93 (16.85)	3.95	3
$[\text{Co}(5\text{-Clisal})(\text{bzac})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	220	44	49.35 (49.59)	3.96 (4.16)	14.28 (14.31)	4.13	3
$[\text{Co}(5\text{-Clisal})(\text{dbzm})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	188	48	56.42 (55.77)	4.35 (4.04)	12.26 (12.44)	4.20	4

Fig. 4. Mass spectrum of [Co(5-Clisal)(acac)].

by Nakamoto *et al.*¹⁶. A broad band appears at 3284–3553 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to the ν(OH) of the coordinated water molecules.

Electronic spectra :

The absorption bands in the shorter wavelength region i.e. below 300 nm (261–297) may be assigned to π→π* transitions. Aly *et al.*¹⁷ have assigned bands at 280–290 nm in mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) of the type [Co(acac)₂(btz)₂] and [Co(acac)₂(boz)₂] (where btz = benzothiazole, boz = benzoxazole) to π→π* transitions. Absorption bands at 306–350 nm in the mixed ligand complexes may be attributed to charge transfer. The electronic spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes display two bands in the region 540–565 nm and 810–980 nm assigned to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₁) transitions respectively. The spectra are in accord with an octahedral geometry around the Co^{II} ion¹⁸. The ν₃ was not observed because of its very weak intensity as it is a two electron transition¹⁹.

Magnetic moments :

The observed magnetic moments of Co^{II} mixed ligand complexes lie in the range 3.95–4.63 B.M. (Table 1) which are consistent with the high spin configuration of cobalt(II) with three unpaired electrons. The values slightly higher than the spin only value (3.87 B.M.) for a d⁷ system may be due to orbital contribution²⁰. For Co^{II} complexes of the type CoL₂L' (where L = acetylacetonate, methylacetoacetate or ethylacetoacetate, L' = ethylenediamine, propylenediamine or 8-hydroxyquinoline). For the mixed ligand complexes [Co(acac)₂(btz)₂] and [Co(acac)₂(boz)₂] magnetic moments 4.18 and 4.21 B.M. respectively have been reported by Aly *et al.*¹⁷.

Mass spectra :

FAB mass spectra of three complexes [Co(5-Clisal)(sal)] (I), [Co(5-Clisal)(acac)] (II) and [Co(5-Clisal)(bzac)] (III) have been recorded and the spectrum of [Co(5-Clisal)(acac)] is reproduced in Fig. 4. The m/z values of the peaks along with their intensities relative to the base peak are given in Table 2. All the complexes exhibit molecular ion (M⁺) peaks, [Co(5-Clisal)(sal)]⁺ (m/z 335, 8.3%), [Co(5-Clisal)(acac)]⁺ (m/z 313, 13.8%) and [Co(5-Clisal)(bzac)]⁺ (m/z 375, 19.4%). In all the complexes peaks due to CoL⁺ and CoL'⁺ are also observed due to the formation of such species as a result of the loss of one or the other ligand moiety :

A peak at m/z 214 due to Co(5-Clisal)⁺ is observed in all the three complexes (I 29.7%, II 37.8%, III 13.5%). Intense peaks corresponding to CoL'⁺ which would have resulted by the loss of 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde moiety are observed in all the complexes, e.g. in complex I peak at m/z 180 (32.8%) due to Co(sal)⁺, in complex II peak at m/z 158 (54.0%) due to Co(acac)⁺ and in complex III peak at m/z 220 (40.5%) due to Co(bzac)⁺ have been observed. In addition to the molecular ion peaks due to the mixed ligand complexes CoLL', peaks due to the corresponding symmetrical bis-complexes CoL₂ and CoL'₂ were also observed as a result of the redistribution reactions :

For example, in the complex I, peaks at m/z 369 (12.5%) due to Co(5-Clisal)₂⁺ and at m/z 360 (5.4%) due to

Table 2. Mass spectral data of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} (m/z values and relative abundances)^a

Ions	[Co(5-Clisal)(sal)] ⁺	[Co(5-Clisal)(acac)] ⁺	[Co(5-Clisal)(bzac)] ⁺
M ⁺	335 (8.3%)	313 (13.8%)	375 (19.4%)
CoL ⁺	214 (29.7%)	214 (37.8%)	214 (13.5%)
CoL' ⁺	180 (32.8%)	158 (54.0%)	220 (40.5%)
CoL ₂ ⁺	369 (12.5%)	369 (8.3%)	369 (5.5%)
CoL' ₂ ⁺	360 (5.4%)	257 (8.1%)	381 (16.2%)
Co ₂ L ₃ ⁺	583 (41.6%)	583 (22.2%)	583 (5.5%)
Co ₂ L' ₃ ⁺	481 (16.4%)	415 (18.9%)	601 (24.3%)
[Co ₂ L ₂ L' ₂] ⁺	670 (2.7%)	626 (6.9%)	750 (5.5%)
[Co ₂ LL' ₂] ⁺	515 (58.3%)	471 (94.0%)	595 (83.8%)
[Co ₂ L ₂ L'] ⁺	549 (79.4%)	527 (94.5%)	589 (56.7%)
[Co ₂ L ₂ L' + H] ⁺	550 (22.0%)	528 (27.0%)	590 (10.8%)

HL = 5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde, HL' = salicylaldehyde, acetylacetonate, benzoylacetonate.

^aAll the fragments have been denoted as positive ions irrespective of whether they are odd electron or even electron species.

Co(Sal)₂⁺, in the complex II, peaks at *m/z* 369 (8.3%) due to Co(5-Clisal)₂⁺ and at *m/z* 257 (8.1%) due to Co(acac)₂⁺ and in the complex III peaks at *m/z* 369 (5.5%) due to Co(5-Clisal)₂⁺ and at *m/z* 381 (16.2%) due to Co(bzac)₂⁺ have been observed. All the complexes exhibit less abundant peaks due to dimeric species [Co₂L₂L'₂]⁺. Thus in complex I, peak at *m/z* 670 (2.7%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)₂(sal)₂]⁺, in complex II peak at *m/z* 626 (6.9%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)₂(acac)₂]⁺ and in complex III peak at *m/z* 750 (5.5%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)₂(bcac)₂]⁺ are observed. Peaks due to ions formally derived from the oligomeric species occur in the spectra of mixed ligand complexes CoLL'. The spectra of all the complexes exhibit peaks due to Co₂LL'₂⁺ and Co₂L₂L'⁺ ions which might have been formed by the loss of either of the two ligand moieties from the dimeric species.

The peaks due to such polymeric ions are quite abundant, for example, in complex I the peak at *m/z* 515 (58.3%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)(sal)₂]⁺, in the complex II, the peak at *m/z* 471 (94%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)(acac)₂]⁺ and in the complex III, the peak at *m/z* 595 (83.8%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)(bzac)₂]⁺ and similarly, in complex I, peak at *m/z* 549 (79.4%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)₂(sal)]⁺, in complex II peak at *m/z* 527 (94.5%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)₂(acac)]⁺ and in complex III peak at *m/z* 589 (56.7%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)₂(bzac)]⁺. In complex I the peak at *m/z* 583 (41.6%) and in complex II the peak at *m/z* 583 (22.2%) due to [Co₂(5-Clisal)₃]⁺ are quite intense, although in complex III this peak is of low intensity (5.5%). Similarly, complex I exhibits a peak at *m/z* 481 (16.4%) due to Co₂(Sal)₃⁺, complex II at *m/z* 415 (18.9%) due to Co₂(acac)₃⁺ and complex III at *m/z* 601 (24.3%) due to Co₂(bzac)₃⁺ species. Appearance of peaks due to these Co₂L₃⁺ and Co₂L'₃⁺ ions can be explained with the help of the following reactions :

In the mass spectrum of calcium acetylacetonate peak at *m/z* 377 due to Ca₂(acac)₃⁺ has been observed by Macklin and Dudek²¹.

Thus, the mass spectral studies support the formation of mixed ligand complexes and their proposed structures.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde (Lancaster), 2-hydroxy-benzophenone (Aldrich), 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka), 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (Sisco Chem), 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (Sisco Chem) were purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol. Salicylaldehyde (Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (John Baker), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (Fluka), pentane-2,4-dione (K. Light) and ethanol were purified by distillation. Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Fluka) was used as supplied. Cobalt was determined volumetrically by EDTA using xylenol orange as indicator²². Specific conductances were measured at room temperature in DMF by a Systronics direct reading 304 conductivity meter using a glass cell having a cell constant of 1.0 cm⁻¹. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (~300 K) on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a calibrant. IR spectra of the complexes (KBr) were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer. The FAB Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 Mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes :

To an ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) nitrate (2.42 mmol in 10 ml ethanol) a mixture of the two different carbonyl compounds (2.42 mmol each) in ethanol (10 ml) was added with continuous stirring at room temperature. A clear solution was obtained. The pH of the reaction mixture was raised to ~7.0 by adding 5% sodium hydroxide solution dropwise with constant stirring. The pH was measured with the help of a pH paper and stirring was continued for another 4–5 h. The solid complexes separated, were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

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